

Study Showing Various Labour Welfare Initiatives Taken For Handloom Industry

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Abstract

The Indian textile industry is incredibly prevalent in the nation's economy. One of the main hubs for handlooms in Uttar Pradesh is the Varanasi district, where the current study was carried out. Both primary and secondary data form its basis. There were 385 sample responders in all for the study. Seventy cluster weavers were randomly selected for the current study, which was carried out in the two clusters of Bajardiha and Ramnagar. 15 Handloom Cooperative Societies were chosen at random from a pool of 350 Societies, and 10 Handloom Weavers were chosen at random from each Society. A purposeful selection of fifty master weavers, fifty apprentice weavers, fifty independent weavers, and fifteen heads of cooperative societies were chosen from among the handloom weavers in the heavily populated Varanasi area. A structured interview schedule was developed and sent to the respondents using the personal interview approach and the observation method of data gathering. For the study, secondary data was acquired from a range of pertinent websites, annual reports, studies, publications, unpublished and published sources, and research. The proper statistical techniques, such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, were used to analyse the data. The B.G. Prasad Socio-Economic Status 2017 scale was used to ascertain the respondents' socioeconomic background, and conclusions were drawn from it. To get the results, SPSS 16 was also used on the computer. The study's conclusions indicate that the handloom weavers' terrible situation is caused by their lack of exposure and illiteracy, which has prevented them from learning about the various government aid programmes. As a result, the government should put reasonable measures into place targeted at enhancing the local situation of handloom weavers.

Key words: Handloom, Handloom weavers, master weaver, co-operative society, Handloom welfare programmes

Overview

The majority of weavers in the handloom industry are members of marginalized and vulnerable social groups who not only weave for their own household needs but also contribute to the manufacture of textiles for the wider market. The sector has a rather decentralized structure. Weavers in this profession are preserving the traditional crafts of various States. The handloom sector has a unique place in our economy. The transmission of knowledge from one generation to the next has allowed this sector to endure. The industry's uniqueness, adaptability to changing supplier requirements, openness to new ideas, and long history are its main assets. Value-wise, the textile industry contributes 15% of export earnings, 2% of India's GDP, and 7% of industry output. Over 45 million people are employed directly. The textile industry is one of the key sectors in the country that generates employment. (Annual Report 2017-18). The 23.77 lakh handlooms in the country employ 43.32 lakh handloom weavers and allied staff. This includes 38.47 lakh adult handloom weavers and related workers, of which 24.72 lakh are employed full-time and 13.75 lakh are employed part-time. About 27.83 lakh households are employed by the handloom industry in weaving and related activities. (2009-2010: The Third Handloom Census). The Indian textile industry is unique when compared to other countries' textile industries. This also

enables the industry to produce a broad range of products suitable for different domestic and international market sectors.

Through a variety of initiatives and programmes, the Indian government has been supporting and growing the handloom industry ever since independence. The following lists the programmes and schemes:

- National Handloom Development Programs
- Handloom Weavers Comprehensive Welfare Scheme.
- (a) Health Insurance Scheme (HIS)
- (b) Mahatma Gandhi Bunkar Bima Yojana (MGBBY)
- Marketing & Export Promotion Scheme.
- Yarn supply scheme
- Diversified Handloom Development Scheme.
- Revival, Reform and Restructuring (RRR) Package.
- Handloom Samvardhan Yojana
- Janeshwar Mishra Rajya Hathkargha Purashkar Yojana
- Pradhan Mantri Hathkargha Bunkar Mudra Yojana
- Mukhyamantri Hathkargha Bunker Samman Yojana
- Electricity subsidy
- Sant Kabir Award

Review of literature

Thirunarayanasamy and Paramasivam (2009) explained various welfare schemes and programme implemented by the Government of Tamil Nadu and Government of India to enhance the income and socio-economic status of the weavers by upgrading the weavers skills.

Jyoti Narzary (2013) in his study revealed that Consumers also anticipate that the government will take several actions to ensure the handloom industry survives. The main suggestions from customers for the survival of handlooms include expanding the number of locations, participating in exhibitions and trade fairs, providing financing to establish a handloom outlet, providing subsidies for handloom items, lowering tariffs and taxes, and enhancing marketing strategies for the handloom industry. Notwithstanding the government's welfare-oriented programmes, about half of the handloom weavers are from the most disadvantaged and underprivileged social groups. Weaver families have a high rate of poverty and illiteracy, and they also have limited access to essential amenities like housing, livelihood facilities, water and sanitation, and health care.

In his research on the topic entitled "Handloom Industry in India: Problems and Prospects" Bhagat Singh concluded that the handloom sector is primarily labor-intensive and has the potential to employ a substantial percentage of the unemployed labour population, it is especially important for a nation with a labour surplus like India. However, this industry has a wide range of technological challenges, including a lack of resources, a poor marketing network, and a shortage of inputs.

If given the proper attention for its development, this sector might significantly contribute to the creation of income, output, employment, and foreign exchange earnings.

Objectives

- 1- To find out how informed handloom weavers are of the several government schemes designed to support the sector.
- 2- To know about several government benefit programmes for handloom weavers according to their place of residence and educational background.

Materials and Methods

One of the main hubs for handlooms in Uttar Pradesh is the Varanasi district, where the current study was carried out. Both primary and secondary data form its basis. There were 385 sample responders in all for the study. Seventy cluster weavers were chosen at random to participate in the current study,

which was carried out in two clusters – Ramnagar and Bajardiha. 15 Handloom Cooperative Societies were chosen at random from a pool of 350 Societies, and 10 Handloom Weavers were chosen at random from each Society. Among the handloom weavers in the densely crowded Varanasi area, a deliberate selection of fifty master weavers, fifty apprentice weavers, fifty independent weavers, and fifteen heads of cooperative societies were made. A structured interview schedule was developed and sent to the respondents using the personal interview approach and the observation method of data gathering. fifty master weavers, fifty trainee weavers, fifty independent weavers, and fifty carefully chosen The study utilised a range of public and unpublished papers, journals, annual reports, and websites that provided pertinent secondary data. Statistical tools such as Mean, Frequency, Percentage, Standard Deviation Test, and x2 Test were employed to examine the data. The socioeconomic background of the respondents was ascertained by combining the B.G. Prasad's 2017 Socio-Economic Status scale with the computer tool SPSS 16. This yielded the desired results.

Results and Discussion

Results of the study were discussed according to the objectives of the study.

TABLE -1
Table Showing Profile of the Respondents as per their Demography

Table No-1	Title	S.No.	Categories	Number	Percentage
1.1	Age (In Years)	1	Up to 30	108	27
		2	31-45	205	51.25
		3	Above 46	87	21.75
				400	100
1.2	Gender	1	Male	318	79.5
		2	Female	82	20.5
			Total	400	100
1.3	Religion	1	Hindu	162	40.5
		2	Muslim	211	52.75
		3	Others	27	6.75
			Total	400	100
1.4	Caste	1	General	48	12
		2	OBC	173	43.25
		3	SC	179	44.75
			Total	400	100
1.5	Educational Qualification	1	Illiterate	134	33.5
		2	Primary	58	14.5
		3	Middle	32	8
		4	High	79	19.75
		5	Inter	68	17
		6	Under Graduate	14	3.5
		7	Post Graduate	13	3.25
		8	Professional	2	.5
			Total	400	100

Table no. 1.1 reveals that the age range of 31 to 45 years was represented by 51.25% of respondents, while 27% of respondents were in the 30 and under age group. The percentage of respondents who were 46 years of age or older was only 21.75%. According to Table 1.2, the majority of respondents (79.5%) identified as male, and 20.5% identified as female. According to Table 1.3, the majority of

respondents (52.75%) identified as Muslims, followed by Hindus (40.5%) and other religions with around (6.75) respondents. As can be seen from Table 1.4, a sizable portion of respondents (44.75%) belonged to the SC category, whereas only 12.0% and 43.25%, respectively, belonged to the general caste and other backward castes. Table 1.5 shows that 33.5 percent of respondents were illiterate, 19.75% had finished high school, and 14.5% had only finished primary school. Of the participants, 17% possessed an intermediate degree, 8% possessed a medium level education, and 3.5% possessed less than a graduate degree. Just 0.5% of respondents had professional training, and just 3.25 percent had postgraduate training.

TABLE -2
Table Showing Awareness Regarding
Government Welfare Programmes

S.No	Government Welfare Programmes	Yes		No		Total	
		Response	%	Response	%	Respondents	%
1.	National Handloom Development programme	181	45.25	219	54.75	400	100
2.	RRR package	82	20.5	318	79.5	400	100
3.	“Handloom comprehensive welfare Programme Health insurance Scheme”	211	52.75	189	47.25	400	100
4.	Mahatma Gandhi Bunkar Bima Yojna	237	59.25	163	40.75	400	100
5.	Handloom Samvardhan Yojana	157	39.25	243	60.75	400	100
6.	Janeshwar Mishra Rajya Hathkargha Purashkar Yojana	46	11.5	354	88.5	400	100
7.	Pradhan Mantri Hathkargha Bunkar Mudra Yojana	49	12.25	351	87.75	400	100
8.	Mukhyamantri Hathkargha bunker samman yojana	53	13.25	347	86.75	400	100
9.	Electricity subsidy	77	19.25	323	80.75	400	100
10.	Sant kabir Award	81	20.25	319	79.75	400	100
11.	Yarn supply Scheme.	231	57.75	169	42.25	400	100

Table No. 2 presents information on several government welfare schemes. The Mahatma Gandhi Bunkar Bima Yojana was known to the majority of respondents (59.25%), as the table demonstrates. 52.75% of respondents were aware of the Health Insurance Scheme, compared to 57.75% who were aware of the Yarn Supply Scheme. Of the respondents, 45.25% were aware of the National Handloom Development Programme and 39.25% were aware of the Handloom Samvardhan Yojana. Of the respondents, 20.25% were aware of the Sant Kabir Award, 20.5% were aware of the RRR package, 19.25% were aware of the power subsidy, and 11.1 were aware of Mukhyamantri Hathkargha. Bunkar Samman Yojana, Pradhanmantri Hathkargha Bunkar Mudra Yojana, and Janeshwer Mishra were known to 11.5% of respondents and 13.25% of respondents, respectively. Yojana Rajya Hathkargha Purskar.

Figure No-1

5. Findings

- 1 The majority of responders (49.5%) were in the 36–50 age range.
- 2 Men made up the majority of responders (83.5%).
- 3 Majority of responders i.e (51.1%) belonged to the Muslims Community.
- 4 4-A good Number of responders i.e. (44.8%) belonged to scheduled Caste.
- 5 Majority of those respondents found illiterate the percentage is (36.7%) lacked literacy.
- 6 The majority of those surveyed (60.5%) were aware of the Mahatma Gandhi Bunkar Bima Yojana.
- 7 it was also observed the urban weavers had significantly high knowledge of various Government welfare programmes.

Conclusion

Most handloom weavers are illiterate, and even those who are might not be familiar with all the initiatives supported by the government. There's a consciousness deficit. They are not aware that the government offers variously named aid initiatives for their benefit. These days, the government is required to enlighten the public about all of its aid initiatives by erecting booths in rural and remote areas and appointing government delegates to facilitate discussions with extremely low-level weavers on their own, weavers are ignorant of and incomprehensible about the Pradhan Mantri Hathkargha Bunkar Bima Yojana. On the other hand, should these plans prove profitable, they will have the capacity to produce superior products that they may sell straight to their customers?

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